

surface, or in a reaction of RSH with oxygen attached to the surface. Unlike the first two, the last mentioned possibility does not accord with the work of Michaelis and Flexner (*loc. cit.*) who found excellent recovery of the 'anomalous' potential from pronounced cathodic polarisation of the electrode, nor can it be reconciled with their observation that the potential is fairly well established with a black platinum electrode that has first been saturated with hydrogen and then washed with nitrogen while immersed in the cysteine solution. In reference to the first two possibilities on the other hand, although the heavy cathodic polarisation at a mercury surface, employed in the electrolytic reduction of cystine, would presumably replace the RS radicles with a layer of hydrogen atoms, it seems rather unlikely that the layer would be sufficiently stable to permit the establishment of even a drifting potential of the normal type.

SUMMARY.

The establishment of the anomalous redox potentials of sulphhydryl-disulphide systems, is attributed to the ionisation of a surface compound, formed by the combination of RS radicles with the surface atoms of the electrode metal.

A simple theory of the 'surface compound' electrode is given.

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Parachors and Chemical Constitution. Part VI. Quadrivalent Tellurium Compounds.

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Lowry and Gilbert (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2867.; Sidgwick, "The Covalent Link in Chemistry," 1933, p. 206; Lowry, "Optical Rotatory Power," 1935, pp. 58-59) prepared optically active forms of phenyl-*p*-tolylmethyltelluronium iodide. This led them to conclude that quadrivalent tellurium, like quadrivalent sulphur and selenium, possesses a tetrahedral configuration.

Burstall and Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 229) determined the parachors of some diaryltellurium dihalides in the fused state. They have shown the compounds to possess a non-polar structure in which each halogen atom is linked by a single electron to the central tellurium atom, thereby completing its octet.

If these compounds do contain single electron bonds to the halogen, there should be a paramagnetic effect due to the unpaired electrons (Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 3229). Actually this will be masked by the diamagnetic effect of the rest of the molecule. However, if there is any paramagnetic effect, it will be shown by the variation of magnetic susceptibility with temperature. Bhatnagar and Lahiri (*Z. Physik*, 1933, 84, 671) examined the compounds $\alpha\text{-Me}_2\text{-TeR}_2$ ($\text{R} = \text{Cl, Br, I and NO}_3$) and found the susceptibility to be constant up to and beyond the melting point. Assuming all the bonds to be electron pairs they calculated the susceptibilities and found that they all agreed with the observed values. Hence they concluded that there was no evidence for the single-electron bond in these compounds.

In an attempt to find the molecular structure of these diamagnetic tellurium compounds, their parachors have been determined in the fused state.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The tellurium compounds were prepared by the method of Vernon (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 86; 1921, 119, 694) and their tellurium content was determined by the method of Drew and Porter (*ibid.*, 1929, 2094).

1. α -Dimethyl telluridichloride, m.p. 96° (Found: Te, 55.55. calc. Te, 55.81 per cent).
2. α -Dimethyl telluridibromide, m.p. 92° (Found: Te, 39.96. calc. Te, 40.16 per cent).
3. α -Dimethyl telluridi-iodide, m.p. 127° (decomp.). (Found: Te, 30.82 calc. Te, 30.99 per cent).
4. α -Dimethyl telluridinitrate, m.p. 142° (Found: Te, 44.80. calc. Te, 45.28 per cent.).

The densities were determined with a U-shaped pycnometer (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1171) and surface tension by the method of maximum bubble pressure using the apparatus described by Bhatnagar and Singh (*J. chim. phys.*, 1928, 25, 21). The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

	Substance.	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	Parachor $P_{\text{Obs.}}$
1.	α -Dimethyl telluridichloride	100°	2.118g./c.c.	43.69 dynes/cm.	277.4
2.	α -Dimethyl telluridibromide	96	2.670	42.42	303.5
3.	α -Dimethyl telluridinitrate	144	1.985	39.15	354.8

These compounds have been shown to contain no single-electron bonds (Bhatnagar and Lahiri, *loc. cit.*) and moreover, the occurrence of singlet links formed of a single shared electron is very rare and such links are always very unstable (Sidgwick, "The Electronic Theory of Valency," p. 103). These compounds may be represented by the following electronic structure (*cf.* Sidgwick, "The Covalent Link in Chemistry," *loc. cit.*)

This involves expansion of the valency group of tellurium to ten electrons. In Table II the parachors $P_{\text{calc.}}$ for these compounds calculated according to Sidgwick and Bayliss (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2032) are, therefore, compared with their parachors, $P_{\text{obs.}}$, observed from the experimental data.

The data for compounds 4-5 is due to Burstall and Sugden (*loc. cit.*) and 6-7 due to Lowry and Gilbert (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE II.

	Substance.	$P_{\text{Obs.}}$	$P_{\text{Calc.}}$
1.	α -Dimethyl telluridichloride	277.4	274.6
2.	α -Dimethyl telluridibromide	303.5	302.0
3.	α -Dimethyl telluridinitrate	354.8	952.0
4.	α -Dimethyl telluridichloride	547.3	542.4
5.	Di- <i>p</i> -anisyl telluridichloride	663.2	660.4
6.	α -Diethyl telluridi-iodide	425.0	426.0
7.	β -Diethyl telluridibromide	377.3	380.0

CONCLUSION.

The parachors observed and calculated are in good agreement. This leads to the conclusion that the quadrivalent tellurium compounds possess a structure, in which the central tellurium atom is surrounded by a shell of ten electrons; four pairs of which are shared constituting four normal linkages and the fifth is a 'lone' pair. This view of expansion of the valency group beyond the normal octet in the quadrivalent tellurium compounds is further supported by the work of Simons (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 3488) in the case of tellurium tetrachloride.

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Analytical Uses of Nessler's Reagent. Detection of Aldehydes. Quantitative Estimation of Glucose. Part I.

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Methods which are ordinarily used for the estimation of glucose are often found to be attended with experimental difficulties. In case of Fehling's or Pavy's method the process is not only indirect, *i.e.*, a standard solution of pure glucose is required for comparison, but invariably gives discordant results on account of the easy oxidisability of cuprous oxide which is formed. The present work was undertaken in order to simplify the process of estimation and to eliminate other attendant difficulties. Our attention was drawn to two papers by Gros and Bougault (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1922, **26**, 5, 170), in which they made a statement that Nessler's reagent could be suitably used for the estimation of some ketones and aldehydes, as an example of which they gave details of the estimation of acetone in urine. It was thought worth investigating whether a similar process should be applicable to the estimation of glucose. According to Gros and Bougault ketones are treated with Nessler's reagent and the mixture, thus obtained, is neutralised and treated with excess of standard iodine solution when the mercury which is formed goes into solution; the excess of iodine is then titrated back. This method